

JIS

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Editorial

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JIS

Journal of Interdisciplinary Sciences (JIS)

Vision

“ENRICHING BEAUTIFUL MINDS TOWARDS INTELLIGENT MINDS”

The Journal of Interdisciplinary Sciences (JIS) aims to disseminate scholarly research articles and papers to the wider community with the aim of offering an academic and scientific platform that provides an outlet to authors. The Journal of Interdisciplinary Sciences (JIS) is an open access online journal. Initially, the JIS will provide an online version, but is planning a print version later in this academic journey. The Journal of Interdisciplinary Sciences (JIS) focuses on a high-quality academic research articles and papers. All categories of research are of interest to the JIS, including insightful empirical studies, conceptual papers, commentary, essays, and theoretical articles.

JIS is an interdisciplinary platform and invites authors, academics, students, researchers, leaders, managers, scientists for their contributions in the disciplines of sciences, sociology, education, philosophy, humanities and management. Articles and Papers of scientific and academic rigour in Qualitative, Quantitative, Mixed or Blend methods are welcome.

JIS intends to publish two issues per annum (May and November).

Submissions to, and Publication in, the JIS is free.

All papers submitted for publication will be peer reviewed.

Journal of Interdisciplinary Sciences (JIS)

mission is to “Guide Beautiful Minds towards Intellectual Enrichment”

JIS Journal of Interdisciplinary Sciences, Volume 2, Issue 1, May. (2018)

Editorial

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Editorial

Dear Readers,

The Journal of Interdisciplinary Sciences (JIS) wishes to announce the publication of *Volume 2, Issue 1, May 2018*. This is yet another step towards achieving our vision. The May issue contains research articles from interdisciplinary sciences including management, education, psychology, and health sciences. The JIS highly appreciates the authors' contributions in supporting the journal's vision through constant interaction and the sharing and dissemination of knowledge in order to reach the wider readership community.

The JIS aims to bring together research papers from many disciplines under one umbrella, in order to enhance access for the wider readership community. To this end, the current issue contains original research papers and book reviews from within the disciplines of educational sciences, management, health, psychology, and so forth.

The JIS has begun its journey with the aim of supporting the views of both emerging and seasoned academics, and is hence a non-profit journal. We are committed to its continued future publication for which we seek constant collaboration, support and cooperation from authors. We aim to build partnerships among and between authors and reviewers in a virtual way by intellectually sharing knowledge and transforming intellectual collaborations.

Our next issue will be published in November 2018. We invite authors, scientists, scholars, researchers, students, managers, and leaders from multi and interdisciplinary area to submit their articles and essays from both conceptual and empirical studies.

The Journal of Interdisciplinary Sciences (JIS) is thankful to the editorial team, support team, and advisors. We also extend our appreciation and gratitude to the reviewers who contributed to the journal's vision through constructive comments and suggestions made to maintain the quality of this scientific and academic publication.

Let us join and collaborate together to **ENRICH the BEAUTIFUL MINDS
TOWARDS INTELLIGENT MINDS**

Mani Man Singh Rajbhandari. Ph.D.
Founder and Editor-in-Chief
Journal of Interdisciplinary Sciences (JIS)

JIS Journal of Interdisciplinary Sciences, Volume 2, Issue 1, May. (2018)

Editorial

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Note to Readers

Dear Readers,

I wish to congratulate the JIS editorial team for taking the step forward towards the next academic life-long journey. This issue of May 2018 is a mixture of interdisciplinary sciences, convincingly enhancing to reach the wider readership. The JIS has also made an effort to reach the vision of enriching the beautiful mind by collaborating with the authors and reviewers.

The May issue 2018 brings about authors from various discipline and from across the world under one platform, which also allows the reader to find and read the research article/paper of its interests.

I am confident that readers from multi-disciplinary and interdisciplinary areas will benefit the most out of the articles/papers published in this digital issue. I am even more confident that the JIS will maintain consistent in their future publications, for which I encourage the editorial team to keep up the effort of continuously search for quality and contribution in their publications in inter multi-disciplinary and interdisciplinary fields.

Nevertheless, reaching these goals implies collaboration between editors, authors and reviewers; I therefore, invite authors from various disciplinary fields to submit their research article/paper to the JIS. Also on this note I would like to thank the reviewers who play a vital role in assessing the articles/papers to enhance their quality.

I wish the JIS success in their next publication in November 2018. I remain enthusiastic in reading the varieties of articles/papers in the forthcoming November issue and wish success in their vision of enriching beautiful minds towards intelligent minds.

With best of regards,

Percy Marquina Feldman

Professor, Dr.

Pontificia Universidad Catolica del Peru

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